

Optimizing UAV Station Placement for Pharmaceutical Transfers Between Hospitals

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Abstract—Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) or simply drones are a fast growing technology with many applications in several sectors, one of them being the transportation of pharmaceuticals. In this work, we study the use of UAVs for transporting pharmaceuticals between hospitals, and we solve the specific problem of the placement of the stations where the UAVs will be based and controlled. The aim of this work is to calculate the minimum number of drone stations required, as well as their locations, to connect a set of hospitals. To achieve this, we consider both the range of the drones and the operational range of the stations, which is defined by the distance over which a drone can be controlled. We initially identify and exclude hospitals that cannot be served because they are beyond the range of drones or stations. Then, we apply a heuristic algorithm to generate an initial set of potential locations for the stations. This solution is given as input to a metaheuristic algorithm that is an adaptation of the well-known Tabu search algorithm. This algorithm improves the initial solution through an iterative process. We evaluated our algorithm through both numerical experiments and a realistic case study, confirming its efficiency and applicability to the task at hand.

Index Terms—UAV, drone, Pharmaceuticals transfer, placement, heuristic, metaheuristic

I. INTRODUCTION

An Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV), or drone, is a powered aerial vehicle without a human operator, capable of autonomous or remote flight, and able to carry payloads.¹ Initially developed for military use [1], drones are now widely adopted in agriculture [2], surveillance [3] and monitoring [4] among others. Their growth is fueled by advances in battery, payload, and autonomy, as well as evolving regulations. Healthcare is a particularly promising domain [5] as drones already transport blood [6], medicines and vaccines [7], [8], organs [9], and pharmaceuticals between hospitals [10]. Such applications enhance their efficiency and responsiveness in emergencies, where timely delivery can save lives.

The aim of this work is to determine the optimal number and location of drone stations to connect hospitals. We account for the drones' maximum flight range (i.e., we assume battery-powered drones) and the stations' control range (i.e., we assume remote operation of drones). Our method first filters out hospitals beyond operational limits, using a graph-based

representation of the area. A heuristic algorithm generates initial station candidates, followed by a meta-heuristic approach, an adaptation of the Tabu search algorithm [11] to iteratively refine configurations and eliminate unnecessary stations. Station selection is critical, as it underpins scheduling algorithms that define drone requirements and manage pharmaceutical transport between hospitals.

In a related study, Huang et al. [12] tackled the optimal placement of drone charging stations to cover customers in a demand area. Stations were first deployed in a triangular grid, then adjusted by removing those serving few or no customers. Simulations confirmed the effectiveness of reallocating the remaining stations, with the goal of minimizing the number required for full coverage. Our work shares similarities as both account for limited drone range, seek to minimize stations, and use iterative procedures, but differs in that (i) we also consider station communication range, and (ii) certain nodes (hospitals) must be covered unless infeasible. Another relevant area is antenna placement in mobile telecommunication networks. In [13], a genetic algorithm identifies base station locations to maximize coverage and quality of service (SINR) while minimizing costs. Like our work, it considers station range, but we also account for drone range and recharging needs.

This work addresses the problem of establishing reliable drone-based hospital connectivity by optimizing the number and placement of stations. The approach accounts for both drones' limited flight range and stations' communication range, ensuring that all feasible hospitals are covered. To our knowledge, this is the first study to combine these dual constraints with mandatory hospital coverage, using an adapted Tabu search metaheuristic to iteratively refine configurations and minimize stations, thereby supporting efficient pharmaceutical transport.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

In this work, we aim to select the locations where drone stations should be placed to facilitate a pharmaceuticals transportation service between hospitals minimizing the number of necessary drones' stations. We denote the space as a fully connected graph $G(N, E)$, where $N \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ is the set of nodes, and $E \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ is the set of edges that connect the nodes. A node represents a point in a two-dimensional space, and the

¹<https://rmas.fad.harvard.edu/unmanned-aircraft-systems-drones>

Fig. 1: Nodes and their range.

nodes form the set of possible locations for drone stations. The locations of all hospitals to be included in the service are represented within the set of nodes, along with additional locations where hospitals do not exist (i.e., nodes can be either hospital locations or not). In this context, we need to select the appropriate nodes from the set to determine the locations of drone stations, with the objective of maximizing the number of hospitals that the drones can service. Each station s is characterized by its range, $stationRange \in \mathbb{N}$, which represents the maximum distance a drone can fly from the station while remaining under its control. Additionally, each drone d is characterized by its maximum range, $droneRange \in \mathbb{N}$, which defines the maximum distance it can travel with a fully charged battery. Finally, there exists a set of hospitals $h \in H \subseteq N$, where each hospital has a location n_h that is known in advance.

For a path to exist between two nodes, nodes where either the range of each node is longer than the distance to the next node, or the range of one node overlaps with the range of the next must exist. Additionally, the maximum battery range of each drone, in terms of the distance it can cover, must be at least equal to the distance between the two nodes. The decision on whether a drone can travel between two stations is based on the smaller of two values: The range of the drone or twice the range of the station. The reason for using twice the station range is that if a drone exits the range of one station but immediately enters the range of another, it will continue being controlled by the next station. We then choose the smaller value. We do so because if the range of the drone is greater than twice the range of the stations, the drone theoretically has the autonomy to travel between two nodes, but it will be outside the range of any station for part of the trip. Conversely, if twice the range of the stations is greater than the range of the drone, the drone cannot make the trip since its range is not enough. For example (Fig. 1-left), consider the nodes (1,1), (2,2), and (3,3), each with a range of 1, while the drone has a range of 2. In this case, there is a path between nodes (1,1) and (3,3) because node (1,1) is connected to (2,2), and (2,2) is connected to (3,3) based on their respective ranges. In another scenario (Fig. 1-right), consider the nodes (1,1), (2,2), and (6,6), again with a range of 1, while the drone has a range of 2. In this case, there is no path between nodes (1,1) and (6,6) because while node (1,1) is connected to (2,2), node (2,2) is not connected to (6,6).

III. DRONES' STATIONS PLACEMENT ALGORITHMS

In order to solve the problem described in the previous section, we employ heuristic and meta-heuristic techniques. Firstly, we execute a pre-processing step in order to discard the hospitals in the dataset that by the nature of the problem are impossible to be served as they are out of both battery and drone range. Then, we calculate an initial solution using a heuristic algorithm, which is then given as input to the meta-heuristic.

A. Pre-processing

Given the drones' and the stations' range, it is possible that exist nodes (hospitals or non-hospital ones) unreachable by drones. Thus, in order to identify these isolated nodes and exclude them, a pre-processing procedure takes place: Initially, we consider all nodes to be stations so that we have all possible paths available. Then we score each hospital based on the number of other hospitals connected to it following at least one path, where the paths are calculated using depth first search, [14] and keep the hospitals with the highest score. In essence, what we do is a clustering of hospitals under the assumption that two hospitals belong to the same cluster only if they are connected by at least one path.

For example, as shown in Fig. 2, there are two hospitals that are isolated (at locations (7,9) and (11,6) - the range of the drone is equal to 2 and the range of stations is equal to 1) from the rest of the hospitals and it becomes impossible to have a path from these hospitals to the rest. Therefore, the algorithm we have developed will keep only the hospitals located at positions (2,5), (3,5), (4,3), (4,6) and (5,5). In addition, the problem was identified that there is the possibility that there are two different clusters (disconnected to each other) with the same number of hospitals. For example, as shown in Fig. 3, there are three isolated hospitals at locations (4,9), (10,8) and (6,1), and two clusters of nodes with the same density of hospitals. In this case, the algorithm will initially discard the three isolated hospitals and keep the hospitals present in the two clusters. However, no path from the hospitals in one cluster to the hospitals in the other cluster exists. In this case, we can apply the algorithms presented in the next section either randomly in one of the clusters, or in both of them separately. The outcome of this phase is the set of feasible nodes in terms of hospitals that can be served.

B. Heuristic and meta-heuristic algorithms

Once the nodes that are impossible to be served are identified and excluded, the nodes to become stations need to be selected. To achieve this, we initially propose a heuristic algorithm. Specifically, considering all nodes as stations so that we have all possible paths at our disposal, we score each node based on its occurrence in all possible paths that can be generated (e.g., Let there be 4 nodes a: (1,1), b: (1,2), c: (2,2) and d: (3,3) and range 1. The following paths are generated $a \rightarrow b$: (a,b) and (a,c,b), $a \rightarrow c$: (a,c) and (a,b,c), $a \rightarrow d$: (a,b,d), (a,c,d) and (a,b,c,d), $b \rightarrow c$: (b,c) and (b,a,c,d), $b \rightarrow d$: (b,c,d) and (b,a,c,d) and $c \rightarrow d$: (c,d). Based on the paths,

Fig. 2: Hospitals (red crosses), possible stations (blue circles).

Fig. 3: Hospitals (red crosses), possible stations (blue circles).

the score of the nodes is formed as follows: a: 2, b: 3, c: 5 and d: 0. Based on the scores, the best paths for each combination are a → b: (a,c,b), a → c: (a,b,c), a → d: (a,b,c,d), b → c: (b,a,c), b → d: (b,a,c,d) and c → d: (c,d)). Then for each combination of nodes we find all paths that exist and score them based on the score of the nodes that each path contains (i.e., the score of the path equals to the sum of the score of each of its nodes) and for each combination we keep the path with the highest score. The outcome of this procedure is the set of nodes that will be the initial solution to the problem. This solution although feasible, may contain nodes that could be omitted, but still achieving drone service to all hospitals.

To calculate the final set of drones' stations, we propose a meta-heuristic algorithm which is inspired by the well-known Tabu search algorithm [11]. Tabu search, starts with an initial solution available and, by performing a series of iterations, generates a set of neighboring solutions, with the ultimate goal of finding a neighboring solution that is better, based on some criteria (i.e., these criteria are different depending on the nature of the problem to be solved) than the initial solution. More specifically, the purpose of the variation proposed in this work, is to *maximize the number of hospitals within the range of a station and minimize the number of stations*. The algorithm uses a decision variable $s_n \in \{0, 1\} \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, where n is the number of nodes, and indicates whether a node is a station or not. Finally, there is a constraint which ensures that there will

Variable Name	Description
s_0	The solution from which we generate the neighbouring solutions each time
sample	Initial solution accepted by the program
bestSolution	The best solution
bestFitness	The performance of the best solution
n	The set of stations contained in the variable s_0
iter	Iteration counter of the while structure
flag	When changed means that while should terminate
neighborSolution	The neighbouring solution
neighborFitness	The performance of the neighbouring solution

TABLE I: Explanation of notation used in Algorithm 1
be at least one path within the range of stations and drones from each hospital to every other hospital.

Algorithm 1 Tabu search-based algorithm.

Require: s_0 , $sample$, $bestSolution$, $bestFitness$, n , $iter$, $flag$, $neighborSolution$, and $neighborFitness$.

- 1: $s_0 \leftarrow sample$, $bestSolution \leftarrow sample$
- 2: Calculating the performance of the $bestSolution$ and assigning the performance to the $bestFitness$ variable
- 3: Calculate the number of stations of variable s_0 and assign this number to variable n
- 4: $iter \leftarrow 0$, $flag \leftarrow true$
- 5: **while** $flag$ **do**
- 6: **if** $iter = n$ **then**
- 7: **if** $s_0 = bestSolution$ **then**
- 8: $flag \leftarrow false$
- 9: **break**
- 10: **else**
- 11: Update s_0 with the value of $bestSolution$
- 12: Initialize $iter$ with the value 0
- 13: Renew n based on s_0
- 14: **end if**
- 15: **else**
- 16: Generate a neighbor solution and assign this solution to the $neighborSolution$ variable
- 17: Calculating the performance of the neighboring solution and assigning the performance to the $neighborFitness$ variable
- 18: **if** Check if the $neighborSolution$ is better than the $bestSolution$ and if the $neighborSolution$ satisfies the condition that there should be at least one path from each hospital to each hospital **then**
- 19: Update the value of $bestSolution$ with that of $neighborSolution$
- 20: Update the value of $bestFitness$ with that of $neighborFitness$
- 21: **end if**
- 22: $iter \leftarrow iter + 1$
- 23: **end if**
- 24: **end while**
- 25: **Return** $bestSolution$

Regarding the Tabu Search-based algorithm that we developed (see algorithm 1 and Table I) in order to improve the existing solution, the first thing to analyze is the way we generate the neighboring solutions. In order to make it easy

to understand we will use an example. Let $(0,1,0,1,1,1,1)$ be the initial solution (the form of the solution tells us that we have a 7-node problem where nodes 1, 3, 4, 5 and 6 are the stations) and the way the creation of the neighboring solutions works is to remove one station at a time. More specifically following this logic we will create 5 neighboring solutions $(0,0,0,1,1,1,1)$, $(0,1,0,0,1,1,1)$, $(0,1,0,1,0,1,1)$, $(0,1,0,1,1,0,1)$ and $(0,1,0,1,1,1,0)$, and let us say that the best solution based on the criteria we have set is the solution $(0,1,0,0,1,1,1)$. We follow the same procedure considering as initial solution the one we found as the best in the previous step. The process of generating neighboring solutions will stop in the case where we either consider all possible neighboring solutions using the method discussed above, or in the case where no neighboring solution is better than its initial solution.

The way neighboring solutions are generated ensures that each is new and never repeated, allowing us to develop a Tabu search variant without a Tabu list. Unlike standard Tabu, which stores visited solutions to avoid cycles, our method removes one node at a time from the current solution. If a neighbor is better or equal, it becomes the new solution, and the process repeats until no improvement is possible. Since each step strictly reduces the number of nodes, previously visited solutions cannot reappear. Since neighboring solutions are generated before being compared to the original, we must first check their validity. A solution is valid if, with the given stations, there exists at least one path connecting every hospital to all others; this also ensures connectivity among stations, as each hospital lies within a station's range. Once validity is confirmed, the solution is evaluated against the original based on two criteria: hospital coverage and number of stations, with coverage given higher priority. The aim is to maximize hospital coverage while minimizing the number of stations. Thus, if two solutions cover the same hospitals, the one using fewer stations is selected.

IV. RESULTS

Once the algorithms were finalized, we conducted four experiments: three numerical and one realistic case study. In the first numerical experiment, we considered 30 nodes, including 10 hospitals. Station range was set to 3 and drone range to 7. Pre-processing revealed that only 8 hospitals could be served, as those at $(24,16)$ and $(25,25)$ were too far from other nodes (fig. 4). Applying the metaheuristic showed that just 4 stations— $(15,4)$, $(20,10)$, $(7,11)$, and $(26,11)$ —were sufficient to serve the 8 hospitals. In summary, while the initial solution required 26 nodes (after excluding the 2 unreachable hospitals), our algorithms reduced this to 4 stations, yielding a 79% improvement.

Following the previous experiment, we consider a setting containing 25 nodes of which 8 are hospitals, the range of the stations is 2 and the range of the drone is 5. By pre-processing the setting, we calculate that from the 8 hospitals 6 of them can be served. In particular, as can be easily understood from fig. 5-left, the hospitals located at positions $(22,17)$ and $(9,3)$ are far from the other nodes and cannot be served. Finally, we

Fig. 4: Hospitals (the red points), other nodes (the blue points) and the station ranges (orange circles).

Fig. 5: Hospitals (red crosses), possible stations (blue circles).

observe that when applying the metaheuristic, to serve the 6 hospitals 3 stations $((2,19)$, $(8,12)$ and $(5,19))$ are needed. In summary, the initial solution contains 20 nodes out of the 23 we have available, since we have excluded 2 hospitals which by the nature of the problem are impossible to be served. When we apply the two algorithms we end up reducing the number of stations to 3, therefore we have a 74% improved solution.

Finally, we consider a setting containing 15 nodes of which 8 are hospitals. The range of the stations is 1 and the range of the drone is 4. By pre-processing the 8 hospitals we calculate that all 8 can be served. Finally, we observe (fig. 5-right) that the metaheuristic calculated that to serve the 8 hospitals, 4 stations $((6,2)$, $(2,2)$, $(6,4)$ and $(2,5))$ are needed. To summarize, the original solution contains 12 nodes out of the 15 we have available. When we apply the two algorithms we end up reducing the number of stations to 4, so we get a 53% improvement of the solution.

We can make some important observations that apply to all three examples and indicate that the algorithm we have developed works. First, it is readily understood that the algorithm rejects any hospitals that are impossible to be served. Furthermore, we observe that the hospitals that we have determined can be served are all within the range of a station. And finally, we observe that the range of each station intersects with the range of at least one other station, which allows for at least one path from each hospital to every other hospital. Thus, we verify the correctness of the results.

Fig. 6: The set of public hospitals in Thessaloniki, Greece and the two hospitals that are selected as drones' stations.

Apart from the numerical experiments, we also conducted a realistic case study where the nodes are real locations of the public hospitals in Thessaloniki, Greece. Thessaloniki is a medium size city (i.e., 19.31km^2) of approximately 1 million inhabitants making it a good example to employ drone delivery between hospitals. At the same time the drone to be used was selected to be Freefly Alta X² which is an industrial drone which has approximately 5km range and 20 min minimum flight time which depends on the weight of the item that carries. Fig. 6 depicts the set of hospitals and highlights the ones that have been selected to be drones' stations (i.e., red/white icon). Specifically, there are 8 hospitals of which two have been selected to be stations (i.e., Hospital Genimatas, Hospital Agios Pavlos) and one hospital cannot be reached (i.e., Hospital Georgios Papanicolaou) given the drone type that was selected. By conducting this experiment we verified the real-world applicability of our proposed algorithm.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We develop algorithms to select drone stations for pharmaceutical transport between hospitals. From candidate hospital and non-hospital sites, the goal is to choose the smallest subset that can service all hospitals. After removing infeasible nodes based on flight and control range, a heuristic generates an initial solution refined by a meta-heuristic. The final set guarantees connectivity within range limits. Experiments show our approach satisfies constraints and outperforms the baseline of selecting all sites. Future work will focus on deriving an optimal solution via mathematical programming to assess the optimality gap, and on developing scheduling algorithms for assigning drones to delivery tasks once stations are selected.

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²<https://freeflysystems.com/alta-x>

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